

Agent-Based Document Construction

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The widespread availability of new electronic sources of information such as E-mail, Internet access and on-line information repositories multiplies the number of electronic documents available. Indeed, documents can now be built dynamically by accessing and combining information existing over distributed sources. Hierarchical mark-up languages like SGML can be used to define document templates that can be dynamically filled in with heterogeneous components. These documents can in turn be made permanent by storing them in document management systems, thus entering the normal document lifecycle.

The Knowledge Brokers project at RXRC Grenoble aims to develop powerful facilities for automating the dynamic composition of documents from on-line information repositories.

In the KB architecture,

- user-driven **Demand Agents** request dynamic documents,
- **Broker Agents** decompose requests into interdependent subrequests,
- requests that cannot be further decomposed are fed into **Supply Agents** that access electronic information repositories through indexed-search engines and query-by-content facilities,
- the results are then recomposed by the Brokers and the documents thus obtained are finally returned to the Demand Agents.

Requests do not need to be fully defined; they may correspond to partial specifications of the attributes of the requested documents. Furthermore, requests that cannot be fully satisfied may still obtain results in the form of partial objects that refine the initial requests by instantiating some of its attributes or by adding new attributes, thus providing user feedback.

The KB project is well-aligned with existing standardization efforts in document management and indeed provides an implementation of document search as specified by DMA (Document Management Alliance), an industry standard concerned with the search, retrieval, storage and conversion of documents on heterogeneous document management

systems. DMA is the result of the merging of two previously existing standardization efforts: Shamrock (backed by IBM and Saros) and DEN (backed by Xerox and Novell).

A powerful engine for developing and executing Broker Agents has been implemented. This engine uses constraints to handle partially specified requests and supports reusability of results through powerful caching facilities. The Demand Agents are currently programmed as standard database query interfaces. The Supply Agents correspond to wrappers to WWW search engines and are mediated through normal RPC stubs. Future plans include interactive graphical user interfaces and replacement of the RPC protocol with remote programming as supported by tools like Java. Lessons learned from our engine implementation identify a number of shortcomings in the current set-up of WWW information repositories, namely their incapability to provide structured information and lack of adequate “yellow pages” services.

References

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